

EFFECT OF GRAFTING TECHNIQUE TO PRODUCE COMPOSITE TEA PLANT IN THE NURSERY FOR HIGHER YIELD AND DROUGHT RESISTANCE CAPACITY

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Abstract

Tea is one of the most popular beverages globally and Bangladesh surged to a record high of 102.92 million kg in the just-concluded year of 2023. Environmental factors play a major role in tea growing and tea plants are vulnerable to water deficiency stress. Grafting is one of the techniques that have been developed to help crops become more resilient to drought stress. The current study was aimed to develop drought resistant tea plants as well as to increase the yield by grafting technique using different rootstock and scion combinations. Hence, the current experiment with three phases was conducted in Bangladesh Tea Research Institute (BTRI) VP nursery and BTRI main field from 2019 to 2023 consisting four treatments i.e. T₁ = (BTS1 rootstock+ BT2 scion), T₂ = (BTS1 rootstock+ BT12 scion), T₃ = (BTS1 rootstock+ BT15 scion) and T₄ = (BTS1 rootstock+BT17 scion) with control BT2. Sprouting percentage and the success of grafting after four months were same but Shoot Extension Rate (SER) of T₁ treatment showed significantly higher than the other treatments. Plant height, shoot-root dry weight and total dry matter was observed the higher in T₁ treatment and BT2, which were statistically similar; but the lower rooting depth was found in control BT2 because rooting system of BT2 was fibrous root while rest of the treatments had tap root system. The depth of root was found highest in T₁ treatment which can be helpful to mitigate drought stress than the other treatments. At third phase of the experiment, all the yield contributing characters, such as plant height, number of branches, Tea Pruning Litter (TPL) and green leaf yield were found higher in T₁ treatment and control BT2 which were statistically similar. Therefore, it can be concluded that, the use of T₁ treatment (BTS1 rootstock+ BT2 scion) will be a best solution to mitigate the drought problem along with more production in drought prone areas of Bangladesh.

Keywords: Tea, Grafting, Yield, Drought, Composite Tea Plant

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Introduction

One of the most significant drinks in the world is made from tea [*Camellia sinensis* (L.) O. Kuntze] which is a woody perennial crop (Maritim et al., 2015). There are a total of 168 tea estates and tea production of Bangladesh surged to a record high of 102.92 million kg in the just-concluded year of 2023 (BTB, 2024). Due to insufficient rainfall early in the season, tea plantations had lesser productivity; nevertheless, from that point on, favorable weather and supporting actions resulted in the bumper harvest.

However, various environmental factors play major role in tea growing but tea plants are specially vulnerable to water deficiency stress. Climate change might lead to less predictable growth conditions in near future, the places where the crop is now grown. In most tea-growing regions, the length and intensity of droughts as well as the frequency of frosts have

risen, which has led to lower tea production (Tanton, 1982) and arise in pest activity (Kamunya et al., 2008). In addition to raising plant mortality to about 19%, drought can result in a 33% loss in a tea crop (Cheruiyot et al., 2009). Many studies have been conducted to develop technology that would guarantee continuous tea production even during times of drought stress in order to reduce difficulty.

A plant's root system is essential because it controls numerous aspects of the growth and development of the shoots. Because it is essential to both the entire growth of the crop and its progress, the root system is known as the "hidden half" (Eshel and Beeckman, 2013). It has long been believed that plants' root systems serve a vital function because they not only provide nutrients but also generate and transport physiological catalysts (Mohd-Radzman et al., 2013).

Tea plants can be propagated sexually (from seed grown) or through cloning (from stem cutting) (Zhang et al., 2021). Compared to the tap roots of seedling plants, the root system of clonal plants is often shallow because of their fibrous roots (Yamasiilta, 1994). However, tea is mostly propagated by "cuttings," which consist of an internode and a leaf from the aperiodic shoots of pruned bushes, because of their higher production potential and quick multiplication. In the tea industry, stenting, or the grafting of fresh cuttings, is a particular approach for creating high-quality composite plants by fusing the rootstock's drought resistance with the scion's production and quality (Sharma, 2011). The practice of grafting tea plants was first introduced in Japan in 1902. After then, it was explored exclusively in the USSR, Indonesia, and Formosa, and it was thought to be very challenging to make the procedure effective. Tea plant grafting has now become simpler because of the advancements in technique of plastic bag, watering, and shading procedures. As a result, it is determined that grafting tea plants has significant practical applications in reducing the time needed to breed a new variety, propagating it quickly through multiplication and replanting and/or reestablishing a low-yielding tea garden. Its feasibility is greatly anticipated in Japan, India, and other nations (Sanai et al., 1962 and Grice, 1968).

Grafting is one of the strategies that has been discovered to help crops to become more resilient to drought (Razi and Muneer., 2023). By regulating the physiological and molecular processes of the plants, this strategy has been found to be a reliable and efficient way to increase the plants' adaptability to drought (Yang et al., 2022). In light of the aforementioned, the current study set out to assess a number of unique graft combinations utilizing prospective scions and rootstocks in an effort to widening the choice of graft combinations that are compatible. In addition, a number of morphological and yield-related variables were evaluated in the grafted plants in order to determine if higher production and drought tolerance of the composite plants were comparable with those of the self-rooted clonal plants.

Materials and Methods

The current experiment was conducted in Bangladesh Tea Research Institute (BTRI) VP nursery and BTRI main field from 2019 to 2023. Bi-clonal seeds of BTRI released BTS1 variety were sown in December 2019 to get seedlings which were used as 'root stocks' for cleft grafting.

BTRI released four clonal tea plants e.g. BT2, BT12, BT15 and BT17 of same age were selected for 'scion'. So, the treatments were as $T_1 = (\text{BTS1 rootstock} + \text{BT2 scion})$, $T_2 = (\text{BTS1 rootstock} + \text{BT12 scion})$, $T_3 = (\text{BTS1 rootstock} + \text{BT15 scion})$ and $T_4 = (\text{BTS1 rootstock} + \text{BT17 scion})$. The 'cleft grafting' for the treatments was done very precisely and grafted plants were kept in completely covered with transparent polythene for favorable condition and highest success rate.

The whole experiment was conducted in three phases. In first phase, Sprouting%, Success% and Shoot Extension Rate (SER) were observed after four months of grafting. Grafted tea plants were maintained in the nursery for about a year until they were ready for transplantation into the main field. In the main field, plants of four treatments (T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄) were planted along with non-grafted BT2 plants of same age which were used as control. In second phase, data were collected on plant height (cm), rooting depth (cm), dry weight of root-shoot (g) and total dry matter of the grafted plants during the time of planting in the main field. After collection of data of second phase, 'decentering pruning operation' was done at 6-9 inches for every plants of the experimental field. During decentering, data on plant height (cm), number of branches and weight of pruning liters(kg) were collected. Green leaf yield (g/plant) of each treatment were collected after plants reached to tipping height.

The Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to compare means after the analysis of variance was calculated by Statistix 10 software. The Bar Graph was prepared by using Microsoft Office Excel version 2019.

Results and Discussions

a) Observations of the First Phase (Sprouting%, Success% and Shoot extension rate)

Sprouting%, Success% and Shoot extension rate (SER) were observed after four months of grafting. In several crops, the cleft grafting led to a significantly higher final sprouting success and seedling development (Saleem et al., 2013). The key requirement for the effective grafting process and the sustained viability of grafted plants is the taxonomic compatibility of the scion and root stock. Scion vigor and its water interactions are mostly influenced by rootstock (Rasool et al., 2020). From the table 1, it was observed that sprouting percentage and the success of grafting after four months were not significantly different for treatments. The uniform sprouting and success percentage of the treatments can be described as the favorable combination of root stock and scion as well as the use of same root stock (BTS1) amongst the treatments.

Table 1. Effect of treatments on Sprouting%, Success% and Shoot extension rate after four months

Treatments	Sprouting percentage	Success percentage	Shoot extension rate (SER)
T ₁ = (BTS1 rootstock+ BT2 scion)	90.80 a	87.60 a	9.2 a
T ₂ = (BTS1 rootstock+ BT12 scion)	96.40 a	87.20 a	5.0 b
T ₃ = (BTS1 rootstock+ BT15 scion)	87.60 a	80.80 a	5.4 b
T ₄ = (BTS1 rootstock+ BT17 scion)	94.40 a	89.60 a	5.8 b
CV (%)	18	20	7.5
LSD (p=0.05)	21.84	23.96	3.48

Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT (p≤ 0.05)

Growth is considered to be the most drought-sensitive physiological process in plants. The process of meristematic cell division generates daughter cells, which in turn stimulate the young cells to expand and eventually lead to shoot development. But under extreme lack of moisture the xylem's ability to provide water to the elongating cells is reduced, which prevents the cells from elongating (Maritim et al., 2015). Similar to many other plants, development of tea shoots is mostly regulated by both genetic and variables from the external environment. Typically, the Shoot Extension Rate (SER) is used to calculate the frequency of shoot growth (De Costa et al., 2007). The SER of T₁ treatment (9.20mm) showed significantly higher than the other treatments (Table1). The variation within the SER of the treatments

can be explained due to the variation of the scion used in the experiment. Wickramaratne's (1981) findings further suggested that the variance in shoot extension rates between clones might be caused by inherited differences in shoot internode and leaf size characteristics.

b) Observations of the Second Phase (plant morphological characters)

Data of plant height, rooting depth, dry weight of root-shoot and total dry matter of the grafted plants during the time of planting in the main field were collected in second phase and shown in Table 2. The highest plant height (60.1 cm) was observed in BT2 (control) which was statistically similar with T₁ treatment (59.87 cm). The highest rooting depth (14.25 cm) was found in T₁ treatment while lowest in control BT2 (12.15 c) because rooting system of BT2 was fibrous root while rest of the treatments had tap root system. Shoot dry weight was found higher in both T₁ treatment and BT2 which were statistically similar. The highest root dry weight was found in both T₁, T₃ and BT2 which were statistically similar while lowest in T₂ treatment. The generation of total dry matter and the accumulation of nutrients in crops are usually strongly associated with crop yield (Rhoads and Stanley., 1981). Total dry matter (14.31) was observed highest in T₁ treatment and BT2 which were statistically similar while the lowest performance was observed in T₂ treatment.

Table 2. Effect of treatments on Plant height, rooting depth, shoot dry weight, root dry weight and total dry matter in second phase

Treatments	Plant height (cm)	Rooting depth (cm)	Shoot dry weight (g)	Root dry weight (g)	Total dry matter
T ₁ = (BTS1 rootstock+ BT2 scion)	59.87 a	14.25 a	10.84 a	3.47 a	14.31 a
T ₂ = (BTS1 rootstock+ BT12 scion)	43.37 c	11.75 b	9.11 b	2.43 b	11.54 c
T ₃ = (BTS1 rootstock+ BT15 scion)	56.50 b	13.25 ab	9.89 ab	3.18 a	13.07 b
T ₄ = (BTS1 rootstock+ BT17 scion)	56.75 b	12.25 ab	10.06 ab	2.93 ab	12.99 bc
BT2	60.1 a	12.15 c	10.83 a	3.46 a	14.29 a
CV (%)	10.94	12.01	8.67	13.03	9.34
LSD (p=0.05)	2.96	2.39	0.09	0.63	0.67

Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT (p≤ 0.05)

c) Observations of the Third Phase (yield contributing characters)

At third phase data on plant height, number of branches during decentering, weight of pruning liters (kg) during decentering and green leaf yield (g/plant) were collected. All data are graphically presented in Fig. 1-4.

Fig. 1. Plant height (cm) during decentering

Fig. 2. Number of branches during decentering

Fig. 3. Weight of pruning liters (kg) during decentering

Fig. 4. Green leaf yield (g/plant)

There is a strong positive correlation with plant height and crop yield in different crop species, such as: wheat (Gao et al., 2020), faba bean (Ji et al., 2022), sorghum (Pereira and Lee, 1995), barley (Scheurer et al., 2001), cassava (Okogbenin and Fregene., 2003), maize (Pereira and Lee, 1995) etc. From Fig 1, it was observed that, the highest plant height was observed in BT2 and T₁ treatment which were statistically similar and the lowest height was found in T₂ treatment. In case of number of branches, the highest number of branches (3.75) were seen in T₁ treatment and BT2, where the rest were lower. Different studies have found a high correlation between the yield per plant and the number of branches, such as: rice (Gong et al., 2022), Soybean (Xu et al., 2021), black cumin (Gashaw et al., 2020) etc. When the tea plant is pruned, Tea Pruning Litter (TPL) is produced which is preserved on the outermost layer of the soil (Borghain et al., 2023). In this experiment, highest pruning liters (47.25 g) were found during the decentering of plants of BT2 which was statistically similar with T₁ treatment (47.18 g). The highest green leaf per plant was observed in T₁ treatment (198.21 g) and BT2 (197.12 g) which were statistically similar while lowest yield was observed in T₃ treatment (184.93 g). Increased photosynthetic capacity, carbon assimilation rate and antioxidant enzyme capacity are probably the causes of grafting-mediated drought resistance (Javid et al., 2011). Roots can significantly contribute to improving drought as well as other stress adaptation and higher productivity. In this experiment, all the treatments were grafted mediated where same BTS1 root stocks were used with different scions. But in case of yield, plants of BTS1 rootstock+ BT2 scion as well as control BT2 gave statistically similar highest results. Therefore, the development of plants depends significantly on their root systems, which in turn control the growth and development of their shoots (Kaysar et al., 2022, Wang et al., 2014, Wang and Frei, 2011).

Conclusion

The results of present study demonstrate the impact of many variables on the improved efficiency of grafted plants. Additionally, it is suggested that nursery grafting may provide a way to mitigate clones' vulnerability to drought. Differences in the yield of a scion with same rootstocks clearly show the significance of stock–scion compatibility. This experiment was conducted in three phases to find out the best stock–scion compatibility along with higher productivity. Sprouting percentage and the success of grafting after four months were same but Shoot Extension Rate (SER) of T₁ treatment showed significantly higher than the other treatments. Plant height, shoot-root dry weight and total dry matter were observed higher in T₁ treatment and BT2 which were statistically similar but lower rooting depth was found in control BT2 because rooting system of BT2 was fibrous root while rest of the treatments had tap root system. The depth of root was found highest in T₁ treatment which can be a way to mitigate drought condition more than the other treatments. At third phase of the experiment, all the yield contributing characters, such as plant height, number of

branches, Tea Pruning Litter (TPL) and green leaf yield were found higher in T₁ treatment and control BT2 which were statistically similar. So on the basis of above three experiments it can be concluded that, the use of T₁ treatment (BTS1 rootstock+ BT2 scion) will be a best solution to mitigate the drought problem along with more production in drought prone areas of Bangladesh.

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